

A Study on Influencing Factors of Choosing Civil Service Career: Trainees in Civil Service Academy

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Abstract

Civil service plays an important role in the state and a constituent part of the system of every government. Without it, the government would be paralyzed, could not function or civilization. So, it is not a luxury but it is a necessity. Here we need to know why people choose civil service careers for persuading qualified and skillful people to choose civil service as a career for their whole life. This study mainly focuses on influencing factors on choosing a civil service career, case study of trainees in Civil Service Academy (Upper Myanmar). The objectives of the study are to examine influencing factors on choosing civil service career; to identify the most influential factor on choosing civil service career; and to find out opportunities and challenges of civil service personnel. The study is based on two sources of data on primary and secondary. Primary data are collected from 400 civil service personnel, trainees of Civil Service Academy (Upper Myanmar) by using survey questionnaires and secondary data are collected from Civil Service Academy (Upper Myanmar) and Internet Websites. Based on survey results, either by 5 point Likert scale question about influencing factors or by opening question about opportunities; Influence of Prestige, Personal Interest and Values, Influence of Family and Social Environment, Influence of Job Security and Stability are most influenced factors. Myanmar Civil Servants value Prestige and have been already stronger in attitude. To be more stronger, Government or Ministry Level or Authorized Person shall deeply consider reviewing existing civil service personnel laws/ rules by enforcing civil service compensation and civil service management systems, especially job stability and security. Like other countries, Myanmar also has skillful youths and people, meanwhile, the government should persuade them to choose civil service. However, choice may be influenced by various factors such as competitive salaries and benefits, the desire to make a positive impact, job satisfaction, work-life balance, opportunities for advancement. Several key factors may come into play and factors can vary from person to person, therefore they may not apply universally. All in all, Civil servants' qualifications and expertise to a large extent determine the quality of implemented public policy decisions and thus the quality of life in the state that is why wishing not only government is able to persuade skillful and qualified youths and people to choose civil service more and more but also we, in-service civil servants will be stronger and stronger attitude. This paper is hoped to be a support for further studies in other fields with other criteria or factors.

Keywords: *Career, Career Choice, Civil Service, Civil Service Personnel, Influence.*

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Rationale of the Study

In a state, civil service plays an important role and a constituent part of a system for every government. Without civil service, the government would be paralyzed, in other words, the government could not function or civilization would it. Thus the civil service is not a luxury but it is a necessity.

People choose civil services career which give them job security more than high paying jobs in the private sector which do not give job security. Civil service has long term benefits such as pension benefits and gratuity after retirement, facilities such as apartments and other enjoyments while private careers offers short term benefits. Moreover right to enjoy suitable pay and other allowance, right to study, right to enjoy leave, right to take medical check-up and medical treatment, right to enjoy maternity benefit for women services personnel, right to submit, defend, appeal to grievances, right to hold the lien, right to serve foreign service in condition are significant benefits of civil service.

Therefore, why people choose civil service careers needs to be known so that the government is able to persuade qualified and skillful people to choose civil service more and more as a career among private careers and public careers.¹

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are as follows:

- (a) To examine influencing factors on choosing career of civil service personnel
- (b) To determine the most influenced factors of choosing civil service career
- (c) To find out the opportunities and challenges of a civil service personnel

1.3 Method of Study

This study was made up of descriptive methods based on primary and secondary data. The primary data are collected on 400 trainees from five Courses of Civil Service Academy (Upper Myanmar) by using survey questionnaires. The secondary data are collected from Civil Service Academy (Upper Myanmar) and Internet websites.

1.4 Scope and Limitation of the Study

It's impossible to cover up all the civil service personnel from the whole country, Myanmar so this study only focuses on influencing factors of choosing the career of trainees in Civil Service Academy (Upper Myanmar). And also we can't cover up all the trainees totaling 47289 within 7 years from 2015-2016 to 2023-2024, thus this study just focuses on 6272 trainees during the survey period, November 2023. Among these, 400 respondents were selected by using a simple random sampling method by using Yamane's sample size formula.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} = \frac{6727}{1 + 6727(0.05)^2} = 399.9 = 400 \text{ respondents}$$

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Definitions of Civil Service

"Services Personnel Organization" is the Civil Services Personnel Organization which is formed with the formation. "Services Personnel" is a Civil Services Personnel appointed to any post contained in the formation of any services personnel organization. Although the

¹ <https://www.rcsc.gov.bt/wp-content/uploads/201711>

Defense Service Personnel and members of the Myanmar Police Force are the Civil Service Personnel, they shall not apply to the members of this law according to the nature of their work and duties.²

The "civil service" is a collective term for a sector of government mainly composed of career bureaucrats hired on professional merit rather than elected or appointed, whose institutional tenure typically survives transitions of political leadership. A "civil servant" is a person so employed in the public sector employed for a government department or agency.³ Civil servants work for government departments not for a political party.

There is a proverb of Mahatma Gandhi "The best way to find yourself is to lose yourself in the service of others". Likewise, civil servants are those who serve the interest of others, exactly, public interest or national interest. That is why, Max Weber also said "It lets the government operate with some rationality, uniformity, predictability and supervision. No bureaucracy, no government". Civil Service Personnel are called civil servants or public servants in other words.

2.2 Ethical Values for Civil Service Personnel

According to Ethical Values for Civil Service Personnel 2021, Ethical Values of Civil Servants are as follows:

- Commitment to people-centered Civil Service;
- Diligence, Effectiveness and Efficiency;
- Innovativeness and Competitiveness;
- Honesty, Dignity, and Trustworthiness;
- Outstanding competencies and Technical competencies;
- Inclusive Participation and Coordination;
- Impartiality, free from corruption, and Fairness;
- Transparency, Responsibility and Accountability⁴

2.3 Reviews on Previous Study

Civil Service in China: Christoph Tarnowski. (2017) on his study of "Civil Service Fever in China" analysis of the condition of civil service and factors influencing the choice of civil service in China.⁵ People in China choose civil service for the following reasons: parental and family influence, job security, gender equality in the public sector, prestige, self-influence (doing interesting work), and opportunity to learn new things in free time. It is more attractive than payroll. In essence, prestige plays a considerable role for China's prospective civil servants. One interviewee established a connection between prestige and altruism, claiming that the public sector was perceived as prestigious because its ultimate aim was serving the people.

Civil Service in Zimbabwe: Jeofrey Mtemeri. (2017) on his study on Factors Influencing "The Choice Of Career Pathways Among High School Students In Midlands

² Pyidaungsu Hluttaw. (2013). "The Republic of the Union of Myanmar, Civil Services Personnel Law"

³ [https://www.en.m.wikipedia.org/civil service, civil servant](https://www.en.m.wikipedia.org/civil%20service,%20civil%20servant)

⁴ The Union Civil Service Board. (2021). "The Republic of the Union of Myanmar, Ethical Values for Civil Services Personnel"

⁵ Christoph Tarnowski. (2017). "Civil Service Fever in China, An Analysis of Public Sector Motivation Among Prospective Civil Servants"

Province, Zimbabwe" studied 4 factors, family influence, qualification influence, gender influence and peer influence.⁶ Among them, family influence is the most significant.

Civil Service in Philippines, Bangladesh, Cambodia, Vietnam, and Indonesia: Yongjin Chang, Sangyub Ryu. (2017) tried to find motivation factors to choose a public service career in developing countries.⁷ They are influenced by the governmental situation, society, culture, and history of the country. Family-oriented culture, high bureaucratic power and network, and social recognition of the job could be significant drivers for individuals to be a public official in developing countries.

2.4 Influencing Factors on Choosing Civil Service Career

By studying the case studies of other countries, the influencing factors on choosing career of civil service personnel are described detail as follows:

- 1. Influence of Family and Social Environment:** The immediate world of people is family. Family and social influences can play a role in influencing an individual's career choice. E.g. If someone has family members such as parents, siblings, relatives and extended family members or role models who are already working in civil service, they may be more likely to consider it as a career option.
- 2. Influence of Peers, Friends and Role Model:** The academic orientation typical of the peer group to which they belong may potentially have a long term impact on individual adolescents' vocational careers. In the absence of proper career guidance and other mentorship, people resort to peer mentorship. Adolescents are easily influenced by their peers because they rely on their friends to provide validation of the choices that they make, including career decisions.
- 3. Influence of Prestige, Personal Interest and Values:** Some individuals may choose a career in civil service because it aligns with their personal values and interests. E.g. someone who is passionate about environmental sustainability may choose a career in a government agency that focuses on environmental protection. Many individuals are motivated to join the civil service because they have a sense of purpose to make a positive impact on society.
- 4. Influence of Job Security and Stability:** Civil service jobs are often seen as offering long-term job security, which can be attractive to individuals who value job security.
- 5. Influence of Facilities and Rights:** The civil service can provide opportunities for career advancement and growth through promotions, training and developing programs. This can be a motivating factor for individuals looking for long-term career prospects.
- 6. Influence of Education and Qualification:** The level of education and specific qualifications required for civil service jobs can be determining factors for some individuals. Some positions may require specific degrees or satisfactions, which can influence an individual's career choices.

⁶ Jeofrey Mtemeri. (2017). "Factors Influencing the Choice of Career Pathways among High School Students in Midland Province, Zimbabwe"

⁷ Yongjin Chang, Sangyub Ryu. (2017). "Motivation to Choose a Public Service Career in Developing Countries: focused on Philippines, Bangladesh, Cambodia, Vietnam, and Indonesia"

7. **Influence of Gender:** For females, the gender bias may result in an aversion to all technical occupations since they represent masculinity. People identified female-oriented specialty areas as more ethical and more caring. Females are naturally weak in physical and afraid the risks. They may be more secure in public sector, civil service than in private sector.

3. METHODS

3.1 Population

There were 47289 trainees within 7 years and 7262 trainees during survey period, November 2023, in Civil Service Academy (Upper Myanmar). Among them 400 respondents were selected according to Yamane's sample size formula.

3.2 Study Design

This study focused on influencing factors of choosing career by 5 point Likert scale questions and opportunities and challenges by open questions to civil service personnel, in another word, trainees in Civil Service Academy (Upper Myanmar).

3.3 Method of Data Collection

Among 8 courses which were delivered during the survey period, 5 courses were chosen and 80 respondents from each course, that is why 400 respondents (5.94%) of totally 6727 trainees are selected by using a simple random sampling method.

3.4 Method of Data Analysis

Data were collected by 5 point Likert scale questions and open questions, ran by SPSS software and analyzed by Frequency, Percentage and Mean for each for 5 influencing factors in which 5 statements for each factor.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Survey Area

Civil Service Academy (Upper Myanmar) is located in Zee Bin Gyi Village, center of Mandalay and Pyin Oo Liwn, meanwhile, includes in Pyin Oo Lwin Township. It has strong and great history since 1999. It was established on 7th February, 1999 so it has been almost silver jubilees.

Many thousands of Civil Service Personnel were trained by regular courses such as Executive Level Officials Course, Senior Level Officials Course, Mid-level Officials Course, Basic Course for Civil Service Officers, Junior Civil Service Course, Office Supervisors Course and Clerical Staff Course, and other special courses such as Special Course for Staff Officers. Moreover many stronger civil servants were also nurtured by the Civil Service Academy (Upper Myanmar).

Since COVID Pandemic era, courses have been delivered in a hybrid form of mixing online and in-house as a modern alternative way. Currently Management, Economics, Law, Social Science, Political Science, English, Information Communication and Technology, and Defense Studies were delivered in accordance with each level of course. All teachers have always tried to deliver contents up to date. Furthermore, it is the duty of CSA (UM) to train civil service personnel to be stronger in attitude; meanwhile it is the duty of the respective Ministry to be skillful in their respective fields.

The lists of trainees from different training courses, who are participating in our survey, are stated in the following Table 1.

**Table 1: Trainees and courses of Civil Service Academy (Upper Myanmar)
From 2015-2016 to 2023-2024**

No	Courses	16-17	17-18	18-19	19-20	20-21	21-22	22-23	23-24	Total
1	Executive Level Officials Courses	30	29	25	20	–	106	80	42	332
2	Senior Level Officials Courses	-	101	111	74	-	168	163	124	741
3	Mid-level Officials Courses	345	170	238	64	-	377	378	91	1663
4	Civil Service Officers Special Courses	1080	1020	836	488	176	388	374	283	4645
5	Basic Courses for Civil Service Officers	370	513	526	516	159	472	486	379	3421
6	Office Supervisors Courses	79	81	83	177	-	1336	2014	92	3862
7	Junior Civil Service Courses	663	995	2770	4351	331	163	162	1744	11179
8	Clerical Staff Courses	577	789	2291	3939	322	1327	2460	1492	13197
9	Courses for Enhance Administration	-	-	-	-	247	486	526	497	1756
10	Basic Courses for Education Staffs	1487	-	-	-	-	259	259	1516	3521
11	Courses for University Teachers	-	-	-	-	-	1428	1523	391	3342
	Total	4631	3698	6880	9629	1235	6510	8434	6272	47289

Source: Civil Service Academy (Upper Myanmar)

4.2 Survey Profile

This section describes demographic data of trainees and analysis on influencing factors on choosing the civil service career of trainees. The study focuses on a sample of 400 staff taken from the total population of 6727 trainees, and requested to complete the well-structured questionnaires. The questionnaire main parts: (1) profile of respondents, (2) influencing factors on choosing civil service career and (3) challenges and opportunities of civil service personnel.

**Table 2: Trainees and courses of Civil Service Academy (Upper Myanmar)
in November 2023**

No	Courses	Male Trainees	Female Trainees	Total Trainees	Percentage
1	Executive Level Officials Course No.14	16	7	23	1.2%
2	Senior Level Officials Course No.16	28	14	42	2.3%
3	Mid-level Officials Course No.9	48	43	91	4.9%
4	Civil Service Officers Special Course No.12	56	59	115	6.2%
5	Basic Course for Civil Service Officers No.66	89	104	193	10.4%
6	Junior Civil Service Course No.97	175	223	398	21.4%
7	Clerical Staff Course No.106	153	279	432	23.3%
8	Basic Course for Education Staffs No.73	158	404	562	30.3%
	Total	723	1133	1856	

Source: Civil Service Academy (Upper Myanmar)

Table 2, describes that while most trainees are in Basic Course for Education Staffs, Clerical Staff Course and Junior Civil Service Course, followed by Basic Course for Civil Service Officers, Civil Service Officers Special Course, Mid-level Officials Course, Senior Level Officials Course and Executive Level Officials Course.

4.3 Characteristics of Respondents

The general demographic characteristics of respondents are described in five characteristics as shown in Table 3: to get a better understanding of respondents who took part in the study.

Table 3: Characteristics of Respondents

No	Item	Category	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	83	20.8%
		Female	317	79.3%
2	Age(Year)	18 - 25 years	53	13.3%
		26 - 35 years	200	50.0%
		36 - 45 years	41	10.3%
		46 - 55 years	88	22.0%
		56 - 62 years	18	4.5%
3	Marital Status	Single	164	41.0%
		Married	236	59.0%
4	Qualification Level	Ph.D	5	1.3%
		Master	13	3.3%
		Bachelor	315	78.8%
		Diploma	25	6.3%
		Basic Education	42	10.5%
5	Course	Mid-level Officials Course	80	20.0%
		Civil Service Officers Special Course	80	20.0%
		Basic Course for Civil Service Officers	80	20.0%
		Junior Civil Service Course	80	20.0%
		Clerical Staff Course	80	20.0%

Source: Survey Data (2023)

According to Table 3, females lead the majority of respondents. Majority of respondents were in the group between 26-35 years and prior to the group between 18-25 years, group between 46-55 years, group between 36-45 years and group between 56-62 years. There was no significant difference between married and single.

Regarding the education level of respondents, the majority hold bachelor degrees and secondly, basic education prior to diploma degree holder, master degree holder and Ph.D. From the findings, it was evident that the majorities of the respondents were educated and chose a civil service career.

Courses attended by respondents were Mid-level Officials Course, Civil Service Officers Special Course, Basic Course for Civil Service Officers, Junior Civil Service Course, Clerical Staff Course, 80 respondents each course, totaling 400.

4.4 Influencing Factors on Choosing Career of Civil Service Personnel

Influencing factors on choosing career of civil service personnel includes 7 factors; Influence of Family and Social Environment; Influence of Peers, Friend and Role Model; Influence of Prestige, Personal Interesting and Values; Influence of Job Security and Stability; and Influence of Facilities and Rights; Influence of Education and Qualification; and Influence of Gender.

Among these 7 factors, respondents were surveyed by 5 factors except Influence of Education and Qualification; and Influence of Gender. The 25 questionnaires were collected based on influencing factors on choosing career of civil service and described in sub-categories. Five-Point Likert Scale is used with strongly disagreed for 1, disagreed for 2, neutral for 3, agreed for 4 and strongly agreed for 5.

Table 4: Comparison of Influencing Factors on Choosing Civil Service Career by Overall Mean Values

No	Factors	Overall Mean
1	Influence of Prestige, Personnel Interesting and Values	3.14
2	Influence of Family and Social Environment	2.90
3	Influence of Job Security and Stability	2.82
4	Influence of Facilities and Rights	2.77
5	Influence of Peers, Friends and Role Model	2.37

Sources: Survey data (2023)

According to Table 4, Influence of Prestige, Personal Interest and Values got the highest score and followed by Influence of Family and Social Environment; Influence of Job Security and Stability; Influence of Facilities and Rights and Influence of Peers, Friend and Role Model. The mean value for peer influence got the lowest score in this study. Therefore, it was found that self-influence was greater than others in choosing a civil service career.

4.5 Opportunities of Civil Service Personnel

Opportunities and challenges of civil service personnel were collected by using open questions then the answers were grouped by their same nature. At that time, these 10 are opportunities that were abstracted by the respective percentage of respondents as shown on the right side.

Table 5: Opportunities of Civil Service Personnel

No	Item	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Personal Interesting and Values	47	11.8%
2	Multiracial Workplace	45	11.3%
3	Public Service Motivation	44	11.3%
4	Lower Strong Competition	43	10.8%
5	Job security and Stability	42	10.5%
6	Promotion Prospects	41	10.3%
7	Pay and Financial Rewards	39	9.8%
8	Image and Respect	35	8.8%
9	Decentralization	33	8.3%
10	Job Satisfaction	31	7.8%

Source: Survey Data (2023)

In table 5, it could be studied that the above 5 opportunities were answered by more people than in other opportunities.

4.6 Challenges of Civil Service Personnel

Table 6: Challenges of Civil Service Personnel

No	Item	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Difficult to harmonizing Work and Leisure	51	12.8%
2	Huge Work Load and Burdens	47	11.8%
3	Lack of Spare Time to Study	45	11.3%
4	Lack of Financial Incentives	44	11.0%
5	Few Opportunities to Make Innovations	41	10.3%
6	Difficult to Make and Accept Changes	39	9.8%
7	No Administration of Direct Manager	35	8.8%
8	Decreasing Self-Confidence	34	8.5%
9	Believing Unfair Promotion Processes	33	8.3%
10	Unfavorable Selection Policies	31	7.8%

Source: Survey Data (2023)

According to the Table 6, it could be studied that the above 5 challenges were answered by more people than in other challenges.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1 Findings

Based on survey results, it was found that, either by 5 point Likert scale question about influencing factors; or by opening question of opportunities, Influence of Prestige, Personal Interesting and Values, Influence of Family and Social Environment, Influence of Job Security and Stability are most influenced factors.

5.2 Suggestions and Recommendations

Myanmar Civil Servants value Prestige and have been already stronger in attitude. To be stronger, Government or Ministry Level or Authorized Person shall deeply consider reviewing existing civil service personnel laws/ rules by enforcing civil service compensation and civil service management systems, especially job stability and security. Like other countries, Myanmar also has skillful youths and people, meanwhile, the Government should persuade them to choose civil service.

1. CONCLUSION

Whatever the survey result, the important thing to be noticed is choice may be influenced by various factors such as competitive salaries and benefits, the desire to make a positive impact, job satisfaction, work-life balance, opportunities for advancement. Several key factors may come into play and factors can vary from person to person, therefore they may not be applied universally. Moreover, Individual motivations and circumstances play a significant role in career choices. All in all, Civil servants' qualifications and expertise to a large extent determine the quality of implemented public policy decisions and thus the quality of life in the state, that is why wishing not only government is able to persuade skillful and qualified youths and people to choose civil service more and more but also we, in-service

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